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SOHIBQIRON YULDUZI

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"Biz kim, ma'lik, Turon, amiri Turkistonimiz, biz kim - millatlarning eng qadimi va eng ulug'i Turkning bosh bo'g'inimiz!"

— Sohibqiron Amir Temur

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ИЖТИМОЙ-ТАРИХИЙ, ИЛМИЙ ВА ОММАБОП ЖУРНАЛ

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HISTORY OF ETHNOGENESIS OF KIMAKS AND KIPCHAKS ACCORDING TO WRITTEN SOURCES

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Таянч сўзлар: Komans, Kipchaks, Kimeks, ethnogenesis, tribal unions, written sources, Middle Ages, historiography, research.

In the history of the Eurasian steppes, the Kimaks and Kipchaks played one of the main roles in the formation of the modern ethnic picture. As from the very beginning of the study of this largest tribal union of the pre-Mongol period, the problems of the ethnogenesis of these peoples still remain relevant. Thus, in studying the origin of the Kimaks and Kipchaks, historical, linguistic and archaeological-ethnographic groups of sources were used. The most developed of them are historical and linguistic materials.

Arab and Persian geographers, travelers and historians of the 9th-10th centuries, in those sections of their works that were dedicated to the peoples who lived in the Eastern European and Asian steppes far from the Caliphate, constantly mention the people and country of the Kimaks. The first in the list of Turkic tribes was the famous Arab geographer Ibn Khordadbeh (second half of the 9th century), who used earlier works (perhaps even the 8th century) to name the Kimaks and the Kipchaks who separated from them. A little later, Ibn Khordadbeha al-Istakhri and Ibn Haukal, when compiling maps, tried to determine the location of the lands occupied by these peoples. Al-Masudi, who was the most educated historian of his time (10th century), gave more detailed information about their settlement, and his contemporary Abu-Dulaf reports in his work about their economy and religious ideas. Thus, knowledge gradually accumulated about these Turkic-speaking peoples on the outskirts of the Arab-Muslim world [1,31-32].

At the end of the 10th century, the capital's writers and scientists of the Caliphate were well aware of them. They were especially widely known in the Central Asian states, where they were not only written about in books that were inaccessible to the people, but also told about their travels to the country of the Kimaks in city bazaars and teahouses.

The increased amount of information affected, first of all, the fact that in the famous Persian geographical treatise "Hudud al-Alam" ("Borders of the World") entire chapters were written about the Kimaks and Kipchaks, and the great Central Asian writer al-Biruni mentioned them in several of his works .

In the 11th century, Gardizi wrote about the Kimaks in his essay "Ornament of News," [2,23] containing information on the history of the peoples of the Near and Middle East, as well as the peoples of Central Asia at that time. Which tells the legend about the settlement of this people, and in the 12th century the main source for studying the country of the Kimak-Kipchak, their activities and customs became the large Arab geographical work of al-Idrisi. Information about the early history of the Kimaks and Kipchaks was preserved in the legend set out in the work of Gardizi. The legend dates back to a much earlier time than the source itself, namely to the end of the 7th-8th centuries.

Written sources are examined in detail by the orientalist scientist B.E. Kumekov. in the monograph "The State of the Kimaks according to Arab sources"[3,156] and S.M. Akhinzhanov. in the book "Kypchaks in the history of medieval Kazakhstan" Despite the numerous written sources about the Kimaks and Kipchaks, there are few specific messages in them. The fragmentary information and description of the life of tribes in different territories and at different times complicates the research and requires an integrated approach in the study of the Kimaks and Kipchaks, both individually and as part of an association. It is important to note that these two tribes were different both in origin (Akhinzhanov S.M.'s version about the proto-Mongol origin of the Kimaks) and territorially, and not a single tribe as many researchers believed, distinguishing them "purely chronologically" [4,99].

The issues of the formation of the Kimak-Kypchak union have been studied better and most fully covered in the joint works of Savinov D.G., and Klyashtorny S.G., [5], Pletneva S.A. [6], Kumekov B.E. [7], Akhinzhanova S.M. [8]. Due to established historical and geographical reasons, information about nomadic neighbors is available in Chinese sources. The historiographer Sima Qian in his "Historical Notes" (2nd century BC) writes about the Qusche, Dinlins, Geguns (Kyrgyz) tribes conquered by the Huns. B. Karlgren defined the Xiongnu tribe "Tsuysche" as Kipchak, and subsequently Bernshtam A.N. placed them on the territory of Northwestern Mongolia. This version was followed by such researchers as Potapov L.P., Gumilyov L.N., Shaniyazov K.M. [9, 16], However, the theory was refuted, and Klyashtorny S.G. in this regard, he writes that "the attempt to reconstruct the name of the mentioned Sima Qiang of the Qushe tribe as a Kipchak ... is not justified phonetically" [10,125]. Some of the most important for this topic are the mentions of Kimaks and Kipchaks in Muslim sources of the 9th-13th centuries. Since the 19th century Their active development and introduction into scientific circulation begins. Thanks to these materials, which are contained in the works of V.V. Grigoriev, G. Yulya, A. Sprenger and A. Vambery, it was possible to identify information about the localization of the Kimaks and Kipchaks and the foreign and domestic political situation, as well as information of an ethnographic nature, etc. In these references, the Kimaks and Kipchaks are listed as numerous and strong tribes, after which the entire Great Steppe is named. There is, however, not a single narrative from that time that tells about their past. Even the legends about the origin of the Kipchaks, which

should explain the ethnonym itself, arose, according to V.V. Bartold, "in later folk and scientific etymology" [11, 156].

The situation with the Kimaks is even more complicated: the state of the Kimaks, their cities and their relationships with neighboring states were known, but there is no ethnic division with such an ethnonym in the Kimak - Kipchak union. For the tribe, which by the end of the 9th century. occupied the vast lands of the Upper and Middle Irtysh region, the Alakol Valley, the north-eastern Semirechye and reached the Dzhungar Alatau, a situation that was not typical. L. Ambis, and later in more detail Zuev Yu.A., identify the Yanmo tribe in Chinese sources with the Yemeks of the Arabic information of the 12th century. Medieval philologist and expert on Turkic history Mahmud of Kashgar at the places of settlement of the Kimaks, i.e. on the Irtysh, in his work "Divan Lugat-at-Turk" in 1074, he mentions only the Yemeks and the Kay tribe. According to I. Markwart, the ethnonym "Yemek" is derived from kimak iki imak - "two tribes of Imaks". This hypothesis has been criticized more than once and was finally confirmed thanks to the discovery of P. Pellew and Hassan Eren, based on which Kumekov B.E. "considers the issue of phonetic identification of both words to be finally resolved. Thus, the ethnonym Yemek is a phonetic (dialectal? chronological?) variety of the name Kimak" [12, 42]. Agreeing with this, Pletneva S.A. writes "Yemeks are the main tribe, the name of which forms the basis of the ethnonym Kimaki..." [13,102]. The above-mentioned researchers have no doubt about the Turkic origin of the Kimaks. The origin of the Kimak tribes is considered in a different direction by S.M. Akhinzhanov. According to his version, the Yemeks are a Turkic-speaking tribe that lived together with the Kipchaks - Seyanto on the territory of the Upper Irtysh and in the Altai Mountains region since the 5th century. n. e. The Kimaks, under the ethnonyms Kumak among al-Biruni and Mahmud of Kashgar, and in Chinese sources Kumoshi - Kumokhs or Urankai, came to these territories from North-Eastern Mongolia and the western part of Manchuria, where they were first recorded by Tamim ibn Bakhr under the name Kimaks [14, 11-114].

In connection with the fall of the Uyghur Khaganate and the outbreak of a world plague in the steppes of Central Mongolia, the Kimak tribes were forced to change their habitats. But these migrations did not occur in a single wave, but in several, which Gardizi recorded in the legend about the origin of the Kimak union. Based on the fact that the Kimaks lived in a territory populated mostly by Mongolian tribes, the author concludes that they were of non-Turkic origin and that they were already in new places, i.e. in the Upper Irtysh and near the Altai Mountains, being Turkified by the indigenous population - the Yemeks and Kipchaks. The version is interesting, but unlikely "...considering the general ethnolinguistic situation in the western regions of Central Asia" [15,277, 281].

The origin of the ethnonym Kipchak, it should be said that the problem has not been finally resolved, but many researchers, including Savinov D.G., [5], Akhinzhanov S.M. [8], Gorbunov V.V. [16,40], Evstigneev Yu.A. [17, 51]., agree with the version of Klyashtorny S.G., set out below in the text. The very first

mention of the name "Kypchak" in Muslim written sources was a message in the "Book of Routes and Provinces," written in 846-847. Ibn Khordadbeh. Using a certain document of the 8th century, he included in the "Book" a list of Turkic peoples - after the country of the Toguzguz, the "country of the Kimaks" appears in the list, and somewhere at the end of the list, before the "Kyrgyz who have musk," little known to the Arabs, are named " Kipchaks" [18, 19]. Thus, more than one thousand two hundred years ago, information about the Kimaks and Kipchaks began to appear in Muslim sources. Until the 8th - 9th centuries there were no mentions of the Kipchaks; it seems strange and leads us to assume that this kind of information is contained in encrypted form in already known sources. S.G. Klyashtorny quite convincingly proves that indeed, the ethnonym Kipchak could not have been used earlier than the designated period, because arose after 744 [19, 125-134].

Examining the stele with the runic text "Inscription from Shine Usu" or "Selenga Stone" in the Mogon Shine Usu basin, south of the river. Selengi, following G. Ramsted, reads in the dilapidated line of the northern side of the stele: "When the Turks - Kybchaks ruled [over us] for fifty years..." [20, 40]. The Japanese scientist T. Moriyasu tried to revise G. Ramsted's reading of this part of the inscription when studying the stele. He very hypothetically suggests reading and translating the phrase as follows: "I heard that the Turkic Khagans sat on the throne for fifty years." But this interpretation turned out to be wrong. Thus, the reading of the inscription by G. Ramsted is the most legitimate, which was verified and subsequently proven by S.G. Klyashtorny [21, 127]. Therefore, the ethnonyms "Turks - Kybchaks" should be separated and read as independent names according to the usual reading of runic texts. According to S.G. Klyashtorny The dominant group of tribes, called "Turks and Sirs" in Turkic monuments, are called "Turks and Kybchaks" in Uyghur runic inscriptions. From this it was concluded that when designating the same tribal union, which to some extent shared power with the Turks, Turkic sources used the ethnonym Sir, while Uyghur sources used the ethnonym Kybchak (Kyvchak). In turn, the Sirs are confidently identified with the large Tele tribe - the Seyanto, who in the second half of the 1st century. existed in the eastern part of Central Asia and are designated in Chinese documents under the name Xie. Thus, early traces of the Kipchaks were found and now their ethno-political life should be considered as the history of the Seyanto tribe. Thus, one tribe is designated under different names in different historical and multilingual sources. All ethnonyms are identical, but what are the reasons for their different uses? In 646, the Oghuz tribes, suffering from oppression by the Syrian kagan Bazhuo, turned to Taizong for help. They complained that Bazhuo was "cruel and lawless, and incapable of being our master." Thus, the Toguz-Oguz concluded a military alliance with the Tang empire. In June 646, the Toghuz-Oghuz, under the leadership of the "leader of the Uyghurs, the "great Elteber" Tumida, attacked the Sires and inflicted a heavy defeat on them." Bazhuo tried to escape, but was caught by the Uyghurs. "The Khoikhu (Uyghurs) killed him and exterminated his entire

family" [22, 52]. To completely destroy Seyanto, the ruling circles of the Chinese Empire took decisive action, sending General Li Tzu with two tumens of Uyghur cavalry to finish off their remnants who were at the northern Otuken ridge and "cut up to 5,000, captured up to 30,000 old people and children, and so destroyed it..." [22, 52-53]. Thus, the Syrian Khaganate (630-646) ceased to exist, and an attempt to restore it was suppressed by China in 668. Such a sudden death of a powerful state gave rise to a legend among the remaining sires about the intervention of supernatural forces. She explained the tragic events in the tribe and was known throughout the steppe. In Chinese historiography, a version of the legend very close to the original has been preserved. "Before, before the Seyanto were destroyed, someone asked their tribe for food. They took the guest to the yurt. The wife looked at the guest - it turned out that he had a wolf's head (the wolf was considered the ancestor of the Uyghurs). The owner didn't notice. After the guest ate, the wife told the tribe people. Together we chased him and reached Mount Yudugun (Otyuken mob). We saw two people there. They said: "We are spirits (gods). Seyanto will be destroyed." The pursuers got scared, retreated and fled. Because of this they lost them. And now (seyanto) are really defeated under this mountain" [23, 131]. It is clear that the emergence of a new ethnic term is associated with the death of the powerful state of the Sirs - the Sir Kaganate in 646, when the Uyghurs and Chinese massacred the Sirs, which caused the death of their state and the ruling family. Naturally, this event, which radically influenced the history of the people, was reflected in semantics, i.e. in the semantic content of the new tribal name. The word qyvcaq - qybraq from the language of the ancient Turks is translated as unsuccessful, ill-fated, ill-fated, unhappy, and is used in the stable combination kyvchak kovy - kypchak koby - kybchak koby. The semantics of the ethnonym is clear, but the reasons for the formation of the name are unclear: is this related to a change in ethnic identity, or has the old ethnonym been replaced over time by one received from the outside, from the use of another tribal group? Klyashtorny S.G. explains the phenomenon as a universal feature of religious-magical thinking - the idea of an inextricable connection between an object and its name: "... the appearance of a new ethnic term is associated with remarkable and well-known circumstances - it was a response to events that radically influenced the fate of the Syrian tribes" [23, 32].

Scientist orientalist N.L. Zhukovskaya writes the following: "The once widespread custom of replacing the original name with another, new name still occurs, although rarely. The first name is forgotten. This is usually associated with recovery from a serious illness and is interpreted as a rebirth of personality. In addition, the new name was supposed to mislead the "evil forces" that caused the serious illness." For example, among the Altaians, in whose ethnogenesis the Kypchaks participated, this custom still exists today. The acquisition of a new name - a talisman with a derogatory meaning - became a means of saving the sire tribe. A lot of time has passed since the appearance of the name kybchak, and the reasons for its change and the semantics, which are hardly acceptable

for an ethnic self-name, have been forgotten. A new legend has appeared to explain the ethnonym. It was reflected in the Oghuz epic. According to legend, Kipchak was the son of one of the comrades-in-arms of the Oguz Khagan, who called himself the "Uyghur Khagan," whose spiritual patron was the gray wolf, and who bestowed on his fellow beks names that, according to legend, became the eponyms of the Oguz tribes, including Rashid ad-din included the Kipchaks. Once, during an unsuccessful campaign of the Oguz against the It-Barak tribe, they found a boy in a hollow tree, and the Oguz-Kagan named him Kipchak. The word Kipchak is a derivative of the word kobuk, in the Turkic language, in addition to the above translation, it means "a tree with a rotten core." There is a second version of the legend: while crossing the river in a wooded area, a boy was born. Oguz Khan said to him: "Oh, be you a prince like me, and let your name be Kybchak"[24.63]. It is noteworthy that in both versions of the legend, trees are an invariable attribute of the appearance of the Kipchaks. In this regard, Kipchak scholars S.M. Akhinzhanov, S.G. Klyashtorny and B.E. Kumekov. suggest that the Kypchaks "came from the area in which the forest is gradually replaced by the steppe, that is, in the forest-steppe zone"[25, 61, 131-132].

This is the origin of the ethnonym "Kypchak" according to S.G. Klyashtorny, however, there are researchers who disagree with it. Garkavets A.N. in his article "Where did the Kipchaks and Kimaks come from?" opposes S.G. Klyashtorny in matters of reading the runic inscription from Shine Usu and identifying the Sirs/Seyantos with the Kipchaks, as well as dating their mentions in Muslim sources. The controversial fourth line of the northern side of the Selenginsky stone, which Klyashtorny S.G. following G. Ramsted it reads as t?rk [q?b] ?aq, i.e. Turks and Kipchaks. Garkavets A.N. reads T?r[k-si]r, i.e. T?rks sir, the writing of which has analogies in other runic inscriptions, and considers the term sir in relation to the term T?rk only as "attributive, when used independently - substitutive, but in all cases the meaning of the term sir is the same: "Sir, Tabgach, Chinese subject " and continues "there was no special - different from the Turks - "Syr tribal union". Otherwise, any of the numerous inscriptions telling about the destinies, big and small victories and defeats of the Turks, imaginary non-Turks - sirs, illusory Turks - Kipchaks would certainly turn out to be their specifically named allies or enemies, especially since no ghostly allies - history in general and, in particular, the history of the ancient Turks does not know shadows, nor nameless enemies - ghosts" [26, 108].

Many researchers and Turkic scholars argue for the existence of Kimaks and Kipchaks in ancient Turkic times, relying on Muslim sources. However, they overlook the fact that the dating of messages in most cases does not correspond to the lifetime of the authors or the time of its composition, because Many documents are of a compilation nature and most do not have originals.

At this stage of study, the issues of the history of the ethnogenesis of the Kimaks and Kipchaks can only be resolved by the discovery of new written sources and new research.

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Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена истории этногенеза кимаков и кипчаков по письменным источникам. Изучение средневековой истории тюркских родственных этносов кипчаков, куманов и кимеков, объединенных на протяжении веков территорией расселения, типом хозяйства, языком (диалектами кипчакской группы), культурой и общностью исторической судьбы, составляет основу концептуального научного направления кипчаковедения. Значимость кипчакских племен для истории многих народов Евразии определяется как несомненным их вкладом в процесс сложения тюркоязычных народов. Автор освещает научно-аналитический обзор истории изучения кипчакской и кимекской проблематики в исторической науке. На основе письменных исторических источников и этнографических материалов был сделан вывод о том, что команы, кипчаки и кимаки – родственные племена.

Abstract: This article is devoted to the history of the ethnogenesis of the Kimaks and Kipchaks according to written sources. The study of the medieval history of the Turkic related ethnic groups of the Kipchaks, Cumans and Kimeks, united over the centuries by the territory of settlement, type of economy, language (dialects of the Kipchak group), culture and common historical destiny, forms the basis of the conceptual scientific direction of Kipchak studies. The significance of the Kipchak tribes for the history of many peoples of Eurasia is determined by their undoubted contribution to the process of formation of the Turkic-speaking peoples. The author provides a scientific and analytical review of the history of the study of Kipchak and Kimek issues in historical science. Based on written historical sources and ethnographic materials, it was concluded that the Komans, Kipchaks and Kimaks are related tribes.